

APPLICATION OF HAMMIK AND ANDREWS EQUATION TO TERNARY MIXTURES. PART II

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Hammik and Andrews' equation is applicable to ternary mixtures of laevulose, urea, monochloroacetic acid and acetamide in water.

In a previous paper Bhagwat and Shukla (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 179) have shown that the parachor of a ternary mixture is given by the expression

$$P_m = (1-x-y)P + xP_x + yP_y$$

where the symbols have their usual significance. The values assumed for P_x and P_y in considering the application of the above mixture law are the values observed in solution by us, and not the calculated values.

The average value for the parachor of acetamide in aqueous solution is 130, while for urea it is about 118 (*loc. cit.*). The values for monochloroacetic acid and laevulose as observed are given below. Parachor of water has been taken to be 52.3.

TABLE I

Parachor of laevulose

Temp.	$x=0.01509, M_m=20.44$				$x=0.0215, M_m=21.49$			
	d	r	P_m	P_x	d	r	P_m	P_x
25°	1.05	65.61	56.02	296.2	1.071	69.15	57.82	307.1
30	1.048	67.92	55.97	294.9	1.069	68.39	57.8	306.3
40	1.046	67.45	55.99	292.9	1.066	67.61	57.79	305.3
50	1.043	66.63	56.03	296.9	1.063	66.68	57.75	304.0

Parachor of monochloroacetic acid

Temp.	$x=0.0550, M_m=22.21$				$x=0.0726, M_m=23.56$			
	d	r	P_m	P_x	d	r	P_m	P_x
25°	1.080	48.84	54.23	86.7	1.106	47.69	55.99	102.5
30	1.081	48.31	54.18	85.8	1.104	47.21	55.93	101.9
40	1.078	47.75	54.18	85.8	1.101	46.72	55.97	102.3
50	1.075	47.32	54.19	86.0	1.098	46.34	56.01	102.6

TABLE II

A. Laevulose, monochloroacetic acid and water

(a) 1.6154 g. of laevulose + 3.1298 g. of monochloroacetic acid + 10.2842 g. of water. x (Laevulose) = 0.0144. y (Monochloroacetic acid) = 0.0544. $(1-x-y) = 0.9312. M_m = 24.49.$					(b) 1.574 g. of laevulose + 4.224 g. of monochloroacetic acid + 10.214 g. of water. $x = 0.140. y = 0.0720. (1-x-y) = 0.9140. M_m = 25.79.$				
Temp.	d	r	P_m	P_x	d	r	P_m	P_x	
25°	49.25	1.123	57.77	300	1.141	47.66	59.37	296.5	
30	48.75	1.121	57.73	297.5	1.138	47.1	59.39	298	
40	47.64	1.117	57.73	297.5	1.132	46.45	59.46	303	
50	47.21	1.113	57.68	293	1.127	55.71	59.5	305	
(c) 2.3002 g. of laevulose + 4.268 g. of monochloroacetic acid + 10.28 g. of water. $x = 0.0202. y = 0.0716. (1-x-y) = 0.9082. M_m = 26.78.$					(d) 2.303 g. of laevulose + 3.126 g. of monochloroacetic acid + 10.32 g. of water. $x = 0.0205. y = 0.054. (1-x-y) = 0.9261; M_m = 25.44.$				
Temp.	d	r	P_m	P_x	d	r	P_m	P_x	
25°	1.154	48.14	61.12	309.1	1.136	49.39	59.34	305	
30	1.51	47.64	61.12	309.1	1.134	48.74	59.27	307.7	
40	1.147	46.77	61.08	304.2	1.129	48.03	59.33	302.9	
50	1.142	46.34	61.19	312.6	1.124	47.53	59.41	307.8	

TABLE II (contd.)

B. Urea, monochloroacetic acid and water.					C. Laevulose, urea and water.			
6.0456 g. of urea+3.117 g. of monochloroacetic acid+ 10.366 g. of water. $x=0.1423$. $y=0.0437$. $(1-x-y)$ $=0.8140$. $M_m=27.6$.					1.6408 g. of urea+10.486 g. of water. $x=$ 0.0131. $y=0.1464$. $(1-x-y)=0.84$. $M_m=$ 26.28.			
Temp.	d	r	P_m	P_x	d	r	P_m	P_x
25°	1.148	55.24	65.2	126.3	1.1305	60.77	64.94	116.4
30	1.145	54.7	65.54	126.4	1.127	60.12	64.92	116.3
40	1.140	53.83	65.57	120.5	1.123	59.02	64.85	115.9
50	1.134	52.72	65.57	120.5	1.118	57.94	64.85	115.9
D. Acetamide, monochloroacetic acid and water.					E. Acetamide, laevulose and water.			
6.1442 g. of acetamide+4.3012 g. monochloroacetic acid +10.26 g. of water. $x=0.1426$. $y=0.0634$. $(1-x-y)$ $=0.7940$. $M_m=28.84$.					6.1516 g. of acetamide+2.2924 g. of laevulose +10.3076 g. of water. $x=0.1490$. $y=$ 0.01846. $(1-x-y)=0.83252$. $M_m=27.26$.			
Temp.	d	r	P_m	P_x	d	r	P_m	P_x
25°	1.164	52.3	66.62	130.1	1.144	71.01	69.15	140.0
30	1.160	51.05	66.55	129.6	1.140	70.15	69.2	140.5
40	1.155	50.12	66.61	130.1	1.136	69.18	69.2	140.5
50	1.147	49.43	66.67	130.5	1.131	68.23	69.26	140.9

In case of A the parachor of laevulose has been calculated by ternary mixture law, in B and C that of urea has been found, while in D and E the values are calculated for acetamide. It will be seen that the observed results fairly agree with the values of these substances as obtained by us in aqueous solutions.